

Enhancing Teamwork and Improving Communication on Surgical Units Using TEAMSTEPS[®]

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Background

- Root cause analyses show communication failures account for 65% of sentinel events
- Teamwork and communication are important factors in reducing medical errors and improving job satisfaction
- Healthcare providers are more likely to commit errors in hospitals with higher turnover rates

Purpose Statement

To improve teamwork and communication among surgical staff through the implementation of TeamSTEPS in a community hospital in an urban area of Southern California

Significance of the Project

- ~ 250,000 deaths occur per year due to medical errors
- Medical errors are the third leading cause of death in America
- Poor communication and teamwork ↓ patient safety and ↑ burnout
- US' nursing workforce will be short of approximately 110,000 nurses by 2020
- Researchers estimate the cost of nurse turnover ~ \$80,000/nurse
- Project facility specific survey findings:
 - 56% of staff report important patient care info is lost during shift changes
 - only 43% reported satisfaction in working with staff from other units

Theoretical Frameworks

The AHRQ TeamSTEPS Framework, used as a model for this QI project.

Rogers' "Diffusion of Innovations" five subgroups according to propensity to adopt an innovation. Adapted by John Hopkins Center for Communication Programs.

Results

Response rate:

- N = 22 baseline survey data
- N = 17 1-month follow up
- 75% response rate
- **Largest improvement:** Satisfaction with organizational reward (116% change)
- **Largest decrement:** Satisfaction with growth and development (-28% drop)

Discussion

- TeamSTEPS improved teamwork, communication, and job satisfaction
- Findings consistent with other TeamSTEPS QI projects
- Change in administration may have influenced results
- Low baseline scores may have attributed to large increases

Clinical Implications

- Administration should focus on growth and development to improve job satisfaction
- Job satisfaction may be harder to improve than teamwork and communication
 - Due to factors such as generational attributes and cultural differences
- Further research should focus on TeamSTEPS and patient outcomes

Methods

- **Setting:** 162 bed acute care, non-academic community hospital in suburban Southern CA
- **Participants:** 24 surgical service line staff from three units (same day surgery [SDS], operating room [OR], and post anesthesia care unit [PACU])
- **Intervention:** 4 hrs. TeamSTEPS training, 3 hrs. of lecture and group activities, and 1 hr. of role playing
- **Measures:** Brief TeamSTEPS Teamwork Perceptions Questionnaire (T-TPQ), Healthcare Environment Survey Job Satisfaction Subscale (JSS).
- **Analysis:** SPSS and Excel. Responses dichotomized to agree / strongly agree vs all other responses. A percent change from baseline response to follow-up response was calculated

Results

Job Satisfaction and TeamSTEPS % Change by Item

Sample demographics:

- 73% Registered Nurses
- 50% From OR unit
- 50% Baccalaureate educated
- 77% > 10 years experience at project facility

For More Information

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References available upon request